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Exploring Pre-Service Teachers' Intention to Use Artificial Intelligence in Education: A Structural Equation Modeling Approach Based on UTAUT2

Juan José Victoria Maldonado, Santiago Alonso García, Alejandro Martínez Menendez and Manuel Enrique Lorenzo Martín

Abstract The growing relevance of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education necessitates a better understanding of its acceptance among future educators. This study investigates the factors influencing pre-service teachers' intention to use AI, employing the UTAUT2 model extended with sociodemographic moderators. A cross-sectional quantitative design was applied to a sample of 908 undergraduate students from Early Childhood and Primary Education programs in Andalusia, Spain. Structural equation modeling results reveal that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and habitual use are significant predictors of behavioral intention toward AI use. In contrast, the proposed moderating effects of gender and academic year were found to be non-significant. Findings highlight the pivotal role of habitual engagement with AI while questioning the effectiveness of current curricular approaches in promoting its pedagogical use, as academic progression showed no moderating influence. The study emphasizes the need for targeted training and curricular updates to foster meaningful AI integration in teacher education.

Index Terms Artificial Intelligence, teacher training, technology integration, UTAUT2, pre-service teachers, moderating variables, structural equation modeling.

I. INTRODUCTION

To promote the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in educational contexts, it is essential to analyze its acceptance and utilization among teachers. However, given that current practicing teachers did not encounter AI during their own training, they may hold negative biases toward its implementation.

Therefore, this study focuses on pre-service teachers who, irrespective of whether they have received specific instruction in AI, possess a broader understanding of the tool. This broader perspective emerges because, beyond their future role as

educators, they have direct experience using AI as students, enabling them to appreciate its potential and educational impact.

Within this context, several studies have examined perceptions regarding the efficacy of AI in initial teacher training. Wang et al. (2024) indicate that when students view AI as a beneficial learning tool, they are more likely to adopt it and maintain a positive attitude toward its integration into their future teaching practices.

Similarly, pre-service teachers perceive AI as a resource that enhances both their own learning and educational practices. Its use enables them to engage in a greater number of higher-quality activities and also fosters greater adaptability in classroom settings (Ivanov et al., 2024).

Nevertheless, it is important to recognize that conducting research with students using these tools raises ethical concerns. Various scientific studies highlight irresponsible uses of AI. While overall grades may be rising, this does not necessarily reflect genuine improvements in learning. Often, there is a dependency on AI without adequate analysis to verify the validity or reasons behind this improvement (Zhai et al., 2024). Additionally, it is crucial to acknowledge that teachers are not merely transmitters of knowledge; the interaction between teachers and students significantly enriches the educational experience and ensures that competencies are effectively developed (Hutson & Ceballos, 2023).

From the teacher-student perspective, a relationship emerges in which teachers recognize the benefits and capabilities of AI but seek ways to work and assess learning without allowing students to misuse the tool.

It is important to understand that education students, both in early childhood and primary education, hold a privileged position in this development. They view AI not only through

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Juan José Victoria Maldonado is with the Department of Didactics and School Organization, Faculty of Educational Sciences, University of Granada, 18071 Granada, Spain (e-mail: jvictoria@ugr.es).

Santiago Alonso García is with the Department of Didactics and School Organization, Faculty of Educational Sciences, University of Granada, 18071 Granada, Spain (e-mail: salonsog@ugr.es).

Alejandro Martínez Menéndez is a Ph.D. student and research assistant at the University of Granada, 18071 Granada, Spain (e-mail: alex189clp@correo.ugr.es).

Manuel Enrique Lorenzo Martín is an Assistant Professor (Ayudante Doctor) in the Department of Didactics and School Organization, Faculty of Educational Sciences, University of Granada, 18071 Granada, Spain (e-mail: mlorenzomartin@ugr.es)

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the lens of students but also as future educators. For this reason, it is necessary to analyze the factors that influence the process of acceptance and intention to use AI, as well as to what extent these tools may be valuable for the future.

Recent evidence further supports the need to examine AI acceptance among pre-service teachers with greater empirical rigor. Samala et al. (2025) provide a comprehensive taxonomy of generative AI applications in education, revealing both significant opportunities and persistent challenges that warrant careful investigation across diverse educational contexts. Complementing this perspective, Ruiz Viruel et al. (2025) demonstrate that teacher perceptions of AI vary considerably depending on pedagogical approaches, with project-based learning contexts revealing nuanced attitudes that differ from traditional instructional settings. Moreover, Gómez-García et al. (2025) highlight critical concerns regarding responsible AI use among future educators and pedagogues in Spain, developing a measurement instrument that underscores the complexity of ethical considerations in AI adoption. These studies collectively indicate that while pre-service teachers may have exposure to AI tools as students, their understanding of pedagogical applications and responsible implementation remains underexplored, particularly in non-STEM educational programs. This gap is especially pronounced in the context of UTAUT2 research, which has predominantly focused on technology adoption in STEM fields, leaving teacher education contexts significantly underrepresented in the literature.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Performance Expectancy and AI.

First, it is necessary to establish how knowledge and the use of technology can significantly impact the understanding of how AI works and what its utilities are.

In this regard, it has been demonstrated in other fields that training in digital competencies acts as a moderating factor for its use. This highlights the importance of digital competence training as a fundamental factor for society as a whole in ensuring the ethical and appropriate use of AI (Vitezić & Perić, 2024).

In the present context, this is particularly relevant due to the characteristics of the population being studied. On one hand, as students, they report improved academic performance because they understand how these tools can be used to their advantage helping them improve their assignments and explore broader subject areas (Börekeci & Çelik, 2024).

If this is the general perception among students, various studies demonstrate that the use of digital tools based on AI is having a highly positive impact on academic performance across all educational levels. For example, in primary education, studies such as Galindo-Domínguez et al. (2024) show significant improvements; in secondary education, research by Peng et al. (2023) reflects similar outcomes; and in higher education, Lestari et al. (2024) highlight positive academic effects.

In this context, the study presented by Lee (2023) is particularly noteworthy, as it shows that while it might be

expected for students in technological fields to benefit from AI, there is a significant academic improvement among students in the social sciences and especially those in initial teacher training programs.

This offers valuable insights into the student perspective. However, as previously mentioned, it is also necessary to understand their views as future educators. From the teaching perspective, Skantz-Åberg et al. (2022) note that teachers who are familiar with working with AI tools exhibit greater professional capacity. They are able to deliver more effective curricular adaptations (De Frutos et al., 2023) and show a marked improvement in their overall teaching performance (Suconota-Pintado et al., 2023).

2.2. Effort Expectancy and AI.

Related to this working capacity, another key factor must be addressed to understand whether there is a greater or lesser predisposition and acceptance of AI: the expectation of effort. This is a critical element in the development and integration of AI.

From the student perspective, it is evident that having access to such a powerful tool helps improve their efficiency, as noted by Khechine et al. (2020) and Romero-Rodríguez et al. (2022). However, this increased efficiency has also led to some resistance toward AI in educational settings.

In response, various authors and frameworks have begun addressing how to appropriately integrate AI into academic work. For instance, Alonso-Rodríguez (2024) outlines a set of ethical considerations, emphasizing the importance of fostering student competencies. Rather than continuing to focus academic tasks on the search for documents, references, or content, these efforts advocate for a shift toward the acquisition of theoretical, practical, and attitudinal knowledge. This approach aligns with the foundational principles established by the *European Union in Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and Council, dated June 13, 2024*.

This perspective, once again, is primarily centered on the student experience. However, from the viewpoint of future educators, pre-service teachers are aware that their responsibilities extend far beyond delivering instruction. As noted by Voogt (2010) and García-Cabrero et al. (2008), teaching involves managing multiple aspects of the educational process.

In this regard, teachers recognize that AI serves as a valuable support tool (Gonçalves Costa et al., 2024; Van den Berg & du Plessis, 2023), assisting in document management, material adaptation, and even generating essential classroom resources. Thus, the notion of effort expectancy becomes essential to fully understanding the integration of AI into educational settings.

2.3. Social Influence and AI.

From a unified perspective that considers both educators and students, it becomes essential to examine the inherent contradictions in the discourse surrounding the use of AI in education. As discussed earlier, AI is widely recognized as a valuable tool for improving academic performance across

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diverse educational contexts.

However, two distinct narratives emerge concerning the societal impact of AI use. One reflects a regulatory and cautious stance, characterized by a greater degree of control and skepticism. This perspective is exemplified in the frameworks proposed by Alonso-Rodríguez (2024) and formalized in European Union Regulation (EU) 2024/1689. These regulatory positions are further supported by empirical evidence, such as the study by Rahimi and Mosalli (2024), which reveals that, despite a growing interest in AI adoption, there is also notable societal resistance. Their findings highlight the existence of a social stigma associated with open AI usage, which may serve as a barrier to its wider integration in educational environments.

In contrast, a growing number of universities, institutions, and the broader educational community are adopting a perspective focused on the responsible promotion of AI. While societal reservations persist, many higher education institutions actively publicize their partnerships with AI providers through official channels. For example, the University of Granada (Centro de Servicios Informáticos y Redes de Comunicación, 2024, February 8), the University of Huelva (Universidad de Huelva, 2022), and the University of Seville have publicly announced such collaborations on their websites.

Moreover, various scholarly works emphasize the importance of promoting digital competencies for the effective integration of AI in educational contexts. One notable contribution is the study by Chiu et al. (2024), which introduces a scale for assessing AI efficiency and user competence. Additional studies focus on training educators in the use of AI for teaching and learning purposes, such as those by Bozkurt (2024; 2023) and De Frutos et al. (2023).

These developments create a controversial dynamic: although there is an open and institutionalized promotion of AI use, this enthusiasm is not always reflected in everyday practice. In many cases, ethical concerns continue to fuel criticism of individuals who employ AI regardless of whether their use is responsible or not.

2.4. Facilitating Conditions and AI.

In connection with the previous discussion, it is important to address how facilitating conditions can either support or hinder the development and integration of AI in education. As previously noted, universities are making significant efforts to promote AI usage. This promotion, alongside targeted training, has been shown to help reduce the anxiety associated with adopting new technologies an effect particularly relevant for women, who tend to exhibit higher initial resistance to such tools (Zhang et al., 2023).

Within this framework, and considering the influence of facilitating conditions, educators generally perceive AI as an effective tool for enhancing learning processes, as reported by Hezam and Alkhateeb (2024). However, there is growing concern regarding the excessive or inappropriate use of AI, which can lead to negative consequences and a shift in perception. In some cases, AI is increasingly being used for entertainment purposes rather than educational objectives,

resulting in a distorted understanding of its role in academic contexts (Kalniņa et al., 2024).

2.5. Hedonic Motivation and AI.

Regarding motivation, several key factors must be considered in the context of AI integration in teaching. One significant aspect concerns the perceived relationship between performance and effort when using AI. Given that AI tools are often associated with increased efficiency yielding better academic performance with reduced effort there is an initial inclination among users to accept and adopt AI in educational settings (Zheng & Wing, 2023).

Moreover, consistent with the perspectives outlined thus far, it is particularly noteworthy that younger generations demonstrate a strong awareness of the potential for educational technologies, including AI, to enhance pedagogical practices. This growing awareness has led to a specific interest in acquiring knowledge and developing competencies related to AI integration in teaching and learning (Galindo-Domínguez et al., 2025).

However, some critical issues continue to impede the full realization of this potential. Koubaa et al. (2023) point out that, despite observed improvements in academic grades especially since the widespread use of tools such as ChatGPT these gains do not necessarily reflect genuine improvements in learning. This discrepancy has contributed to a growing sense of personal disillusionment with AI, often fueled by broader societal critiques, as discussed by Rahimi and Mosalli (2024), Alonso-Rodríguez (2024), and Zhang et al. (2023).

2.6. Price Value and Behavioural intention.

This is one of the most complex aspects to define and interpret within the context of AI integration. The perceived cost of AI depends on several variables, including the specific tool, its quality, and the manner in which it is utilized. While users may not always be willing to pay for a particular technology or at a given price point, they may nonetheless perceive the cost as fair an assessment that significantly influences both their intention to use and actual usage behavior (Venkatesh et al., 2012).

In this regard, the study by Romero-Rodríguez et al. (2023) provides valuable insight, demonstrating that perceived fairness of price plays a critical role. When users believe the cost of AI tools is reasonable, they exhibit a greater intention to adopt and utilize them in educational settings.

2.7. Habit of use of AI and Behavioural intention.

The final factor examined in relation to the intention to use AI is the role of habitual use. University students frequently engage with AI tools for a variety of purposes, as highlighted by Clemente-Alcocer et al. (2024), and this habitual engagement tends to reinforce their continued use over time.

Furthermore, the integration of AI in educational settings presents a significant opportunity to personalize learning and address the individual needs of students. A systematic review conducted by Suconota-Pintado et al. underscores the potential

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of AI to enhance such personalization by offering tailored activity recommendations and feedback aligned with each learner's specific requirements.

Nevertheless, the successful implementation of these technologies in school environments depends not only on their availability but also on the professional commitment of educators to engage in training and adapt to these new tools. As noted by Cukurova et al. (2023), while teacher confidence and the quality of technological products are important factors, they are not sufficient on their own. It is essential to reduce additional workload and establish adequate support mechanisms to facilitate the adoption of AI in educational institutions.

Moreover, the acceptance of AI in schools is influenced by perceptions of its utility and fairness. Karran et al. (2024) emphasize that this acceptance is a complex process that requires careful evaluation of AI's practical applications, as well as consideration of the perspectives of all stakeholders involved.

However, it must also be acknowledged that, despite generally positive perceptions, there are scenarios in which AI can have detrimental effects. A lack of understanding of the tools themselves can lead to resistance; while educators may be able to use AI under certain conditions, without adequate knowledge, long-term adoption is unlikely to be sustainable.

2.8. Sex as a moderator of the relationships.

In examining sociodemographic factors, gender emerges as a key differentiator in understanding AI acceptance. Various authors have approached this issue from different perspectives.

From a scientific standpoint, De-Vicente-Yagüe-Jara et al. (2023) argue that women tend to exhibit higher levels of creativity, which directly influences their engagement with AI. Women are reportedly more likely to use AI for creative purposes.

From another angle, men generally show greater interest in technology and science, which is reflected in enrollment statistics approximately 70% of students in STEM fields in Spanish universities are male. In contrast, in the context of this study (students enrolled in Early Childhood and Primary Education degrees), around 70% of the population is female. According to Karan-Romero et al. (2023), this gender imbalance contributes to a higher predisposition among men to engage with AI-related tasks.

Finally, a growing body of research suggests that while there may be observable gender differences in AI usage patterns, these do not necessarily translate into differences in self-perception regarding AI competence (Monzon & Hair, 2025; Li et al., 2025; Chiu et al., 2023).

2.9. Academic Year as moderator.

Finally, we highlight the role of the academic year as a moderating factor in the various relationships established.

In the undergraduate programs analyzed, students typically take a course on technological resources, tailored either to early childhood or primary education. However, within the

Andalusian context, there is no specific course that addresses key aspects for enhancing the efficiency of Artificial Intelligence. Topics such as programming or computational thinking are not covered in depth.

Nonetheless, several studies have explored similar dynamics with other technologies. These courses often help students understand the capabilities of educational technologies and familiarize them with the tools available at the university. As a result, students themselves tend to attribute greater value to these technologies (Gómez-García et al., 2021).

This connection between technological knowledge, university-provided access, and perceived value is especially relevant when considering factors such as cost and usage habits. Once students recognize that a technology holds substantial economic value and is readily available to them, they are more likely to adopt it (Rodríguez-Gil, 2024; Rodríguez et al., 2023; Xie et al., 2024).

In this regard, the academic year appears to be a key factor in understanding pre-service teachers' acceptance of technology. Even though the course does not directly address AI development, its impact on the adoption of other technologies suggests it plays a significant role in shaping students' technological engagement.

III. HYPOTHESES.

To guide the development of this study, several hypotheses are proposed, as represented in Figure 1. H1 posits that performance expectancy from using AI positively influences the intention to use it. H2 suggests that as tasks become easier to complete through AI (effort expectancy), users are more inclined to adopt it. H3 addresses the presence of negative social influence, hypothesizing that it contributes to resistance against AI usage. H4 proposes that the presence of facilitating conditions encourages continued use of AI, with two moderating variables: H4a states that this relationship is influenced by gender, and H4b posits that it varies depending on the student's academic year. H5 suggests that hedonic motivation enjoyment or satisfaction derived from using AI affects the intention to use it, with H5a indicating a moderating effect of gender and H5b identifying academic year as a further moderating factor. H6 hypothesizes that a positive perception of the cost of AI use leads to greater future usage intentions, with H6a and H6b introducing gender and academic year, respectively, as moderators of this relationship. Finally, H7 asserts that habitual AI use influences future engagement with such tools in educational practices, with H7a suggesting gender as a moderating variable and H7b proposing that academic year also modulates this relationship (Figure 1).

The selection of gender and academic year as moderating variables is grounded in established technology acceptance research. Gender has been consistently identified as a significant moderator in UTAUT studies, with evidence suggesting differential patterns in technology anxiety, perceived usefulness, and adoption behaviors between male and female users (Venkatesh et al., 2003; Zhang et al., 2023).

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However, emerging research on AI-specific contexts presents mixed findings. While traditional digital technologies have shown gender-based differences, the pervasive nature of generative AI tools and their integration into everyday academic practices may diminish these effects (Gómez-García et al., 2025). Similarly, academic year is proposed as a moderator based on the assumption that curricular progression exposes students to increasing levels of pedagogical training and AI applications in educational contexts. Yet, recent evidence suggests that formal teacher education programs may not be adequately addressing AI literacy and pedagogical integration (Ruiz Viruel et al., 2025), potentially resulting in minimal variation across academic years. Given these theoretical tensions and the lack of consistent empirical support for these moderators in AI acceptance research within teacher education contexts, it is plausible that both gender and academic year may exhibit null moderating effects. Testing these hypotheses will therefore contribute to clarifying whether traditional UTAUT2 moderators remain relevant in the specific context of AI adoption among pre-service teachers.

IV OBJETIVOS

V METHODOLOGY

To address the previously stated objectives, a cross-sectional descriptive research design with a quantitative approach was employed (Cvetkovic-Vega et al., 2021). The relationships among variables were analyzed using a structural equation modeling framework (M-SEM), which enabled the development of a predictive model based on data collected at a specific point in time specifically, between October 2024 and February 2025.

5.1. Participants

A non-probabilistic convenience sampling method was used for data collection (Hernández-González, 2021). While this approach does not ensure representation across all population groups, it allows for the acquisition of a sufficiently representative sample to generalize the findings. The final sample consisted of 908 undergraduate students enrolled in

Early Childhood and Primary Education degree programs at the University of Granada. This sample achieved a confidence level exceeding 95% with a 5% margin of error.

Regarding the sociodemographic variables considered in this study, it is important to note that by the third year of their degree programs, all students are expected to have completed the Educational Technology course an element that could potentially explain significant differences, if found. Additionally, although the study was conducted across Faculties of Education throughout the Andalusian region, and institutional affiliation is not analyzed as an independent variable, it is important to acknowledge the demographic characteristics of the sample. Specifically, there is a notable gender imbalance, with women comprising approximately 70% of the participants consistent with the broader gender distribution within these degree programs.

The final sample consisted of 230 male students (25.3%) and 678 female students (74.7%), reflecting the typical gender distribution within the target population. With respect to academic year, efforts were made to ensure a minimum of 100 participants per year to enable meaningful comparative analyses. The distribution by year was as follows: first year 338 students (37.2%), second year 220 students (24.2%), third year 130 students (14.3%), and fourth year 220 students (24.2%).

5.2. Research Instrument

The instrument used to address the study's objectives was the Acceptance and Use of Information Technology: Extending the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT2), developed by Venkatesh et al. (2013). This tool is designed to assess users' acceptance of and behavioral intention toward technology use, particularly from the perspective of the end user or consumer.

Due to its flexibility and adaptability, the UTAUT2 model has been employed in various studies to explore students' attitudes toward AI in diverse educational contexts (Romero-Rodríguez et al., 2023; Cabero-Almenara et al., 2024; Acosta-Enriquez et al., 2024). In this study, the model supports the formulation of hypothetical relationships outlined in the theoretical framework, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2
UTAUT2 Model

From: Venkatesh et al. (2013) (p.160).

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This model stands out as a reference for technology acceptance among pre-service teachers for various reasons, as supported by the scientific literature. First, as previously mentioned, it has been widely used in prior research, making questionnaire adaptation unnecessary. The primary reference for this study was the work of Cabero-Almenara et al. (2024).

Regarding other specific technology acceptance models, only one alternative tool was found to be suitable for the target population and research objectives is the “Teacher Artificial Intelligence (AI) Competence Self-Efficacy (TAICS) Scale” proposed by Chiu et al. (2024). However, this scale was published after the adaptation of the instrument used in the present study and lacks a validated Spanish translation.

Other models, such as the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) or the Theory of Planned Behavior, were ultimately dismissed. The UTAUT2 was preferred due to its inclusion of the Experience variable, which holds particular significance for this study. Since both university degree programs include a course on technological resources, third- and fourth-year students were expected to exhibit higher levels of technology acceptance a hypothesis previously outlined in this research.

Thus, the selected instrument effectively addresses the objectives of this research, and its utility is well-supported in the scientific literature through similar studies, thereby lending methodological rigor to the present investigation.

5.3. Statistical Tools.

To develop the various statistical relationships proposed in this study, different software tools were employed based on the specific requirements of each analysis. Specifically, SPSS version 28 (institutional access) and RStudio were used to conduct the statistical procedures.

5.3.1 Normality, reliability and validity assessment.

First, both univariate and multivariate normality distributions were examined. For univariate distribution, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests were applied, along with assessments of skewness and kurtosis. All variables returned statistically significant results on the normality tests; however, both skewness and kurtosis values remained within acceptable ranges (see Table 1).

Table 1
Normality Assessment

Ítem	M	DT	K-S-L	S-W	Asimetría	Kurtosis
PE1	4,1 6	0,84 4	,252** *	,799** *	-1,097	1,635
PE2	4,1 7	0,84 2	,255** *	,795** *	-1,126	1,670
PE3	3,5 5	1,07 2	,210** *	,897** *	-0,414	-0,457
EE1	3,9 8	0,84 2	,259** *	,844** *	-0,658	0,367
EE2	3,8 8	0,86 4	,265** *	,854** *	-0,635	0,437

EE3	3,9 9	0,85 7	,264** *	,841** *	-0,734	0,485
EE4	3,8 6	0,87 1	,267** *	,859** *	-0,593	0,233
SI1	3,2 5	0,96 9	,250** *	,887** *	-0,081	0,012
SI2	3,2 4	0,95 2	,257** *	,881** *	-0,088	0,128
SI3	3,1 7	0,96 0	,259** *	,879** *	-0,090	0,175
FC1	4,0 4	0,81 3	,283** *	,823** *	-0,798	0,757
FC2	3,7 9	0,88 7	,258** *	,870** *	-0,461	-0,181
FC3	4,0 7	0,75 6	,279** *	,816** *	-0,714	0,973
FC4	3,9 0	0,83 5	,305** *	,833** *	-0,775	0,754
HM1	3,8 1	0,86 9	,215** *	,859** *	-0,330	-0,039
HM2	3,8 3	0,81 1	,249** *	,854** *	-0,341	0,104
HM3	3,7 6	0,85 6	,223** *	,864** *	-0,292	-0,031
PV1	3,3 5	0,93 7	,247** *	,887** *	-0,066	-0,062
PV2	3,4 1	0,88 8	,263** *	,870** *	-0,060	0,157
PV3	3,4 1	0,87 7	,266** *	,867** *	-0,049	0,200
HT1	3,2 8	1,16 7	,193** *	,908** *	-0,317	-0,683
HT2	2,4 3	1,24 8	,200** *	,878** *	0,507	-0,773
HT3	3,1 2	1,02 3	,219** *	,904** *	-0,219	-0,262
BI1	3,8 7	0,83 7	,279** *	,843** *	-0,714	0,936
BI2	3,0 1	1,05 6	,193** *	,914** *	0,023	-0,499
BI3	3,4 5	0,97 9	,227** *	,887** *	-0,501	0,077

Following the univariate normality analysis, which showed skewness and kurtosis values within acceptable limits despite the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests indicating non-normality, multivariate normality was assessed using Mardia's test. The results revealed that multivariate normality could not be assumed, as Mardia's kurtosis was significantly lower than the expected value of $p(p + 2)$, where p is the number of items. This result suggests a platykurtic distribution.

After assessing normality, a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted to evaluate the reliability and validity of the instrument. The findings indicate that both Cronbach's Alpha and McDonald's Omega values exceeded the acceptable threshold of 0.70 across all dimensions, supporting internal consistency. Furthermore, the Average Variance Extracted

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(AVE) and Composite Reliability (CR) values were acceptable for all constructs, with the exception of the AVE for the Performance Expectancy dimension. However, in accordance with Hair et al. (2016), an AVE value may still be considered acceptable if it exceeds 0.40 and the corresponding CR is greater than 0.60. Since this condition is met, the construct is deemed valid, and the overall measurement model is considered reliable.

Table 2
Fiability assessment.

Dimensio n	Ite m	λ	R2	AV E	α	ω	CR
Performan ce	PE1	0,71	0,49	0,45	,71	,71	0,71
		3	2	8	2	3	7
	Expectanc y	PE2	0,63	0,59			
		9	2				
	PE3	0,67	0,54				
		8	0				
Effort Expectanc y	EE1	0,72	0,48	0,59	,85	,85	0,85
		1	0	1	5	5	1
	EE2	0,85	0,26				
		5	9				
	EE3	0,70	0,50				
		2	7				
	EE4	0,78	0,37				
		8	9				
Social Influence	SI1	0,82	0,32	0,70	,87	,88	0,87
		1	6	9	9	0	9
	SI2	0,86	0,24				
		8	7				
	SI3	0,83	0,29				
		7	9				
Facilitatin g Condition s	FC1	0,65	0,57	0,42	,74	,74	0,74
		6	0	0	2	6	2
	FC2	0,73	0,46				
		5	0				
	FC3	0,63	0,59				
		8	3				
	FC4	0,55	0,69				
		3	4				
Hedonic Motivatio n	HM	0,84	0,28	0,70	,87	,87	0,87
		1	5	5	6	8	7
	HM	0,86	0,25				
		2	5	2			
	HM	0,80	0,34				
		2	8	7			
Price Value	PV	0,8	0,36	0,71	,88	,88	0,88
		1	0	3	1	1	2
	PV	0,86	0,25				
		2	6	0			
	PV	0,86	0,24				
		3	7	8			
Habit	HT	0,88	0,22	0,54	,76	,77	0,77
		1	1	4	0	6	9
	HT	0,60	0,63				
		2	3	6			
	HT	0,69	0,52				
		3	3	0			

Behaviour al	BE	0,8	0,36	0,56	,79	,81	0,79
	H 1		0	8	6	6	7
Intention	BE	0,69	0,51				
	H 2	9	1				
	BE	0,76	0,42				
	H 3		2				

VI RESULTS

With the analysis parameters established, a structural equation modeling approach (M-SEM) was employed using the Diagonally Weighted Least Squares (DWLS) estimation method. This method was selected due to its suitability for Likert-scale data that do not meet the assumptions of normality, particularly regarding skewness and kurtosis (Li, 2016).

To assess model fit, several indices were calculated. Although the Chi-square test yielded a statistically significant result ($\chi^2 = 1743.121$, $df = 471$, $p = .000$), this test is known to be highly sensitive to large sample sizes and should therefore be interpreted with caution. Despite the apparent discrepancy between the data and the theoretical model, other fit indices offer a more comprehensive evaluation. The ratio of χ^2 to degrees of freedom ($\chi^2/df = 3.700$) is considered acceptable. Bentler (1990) suggests that values below 5 may still indicate a reasonable fit, particularly in models with relatively few degrees of freedom and large samples. This interpretation is further supported by Hu and Bentler (1999), who argue that such conditions can justify χ^2/df values approaching 5.

Continuing with the model fit indices, the Goodness-of-Fit Index (GFI) yielded a value of 0.961, while its adjusted version (AGFI) reached 0.951. Both exceed the commonly recommended threshold of 0.90, which is considered indicative of good model fit especially given the simplicity of the model relative to the sample size. Additional model fit measures include the Root Mean Square Residual (RMR = 0.075) and its standardized version (SRMR = 0.061), both of which fall within acceptable limits. In particular, SRMR values below 0.08 are considered ideal, with values under 0.09 still acceptable.

Finally, the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) was calculated at 0.055, with a 95% confidence interval ranging from 0.052 to 0.057. This value falls well below the conventional upper threshold of 0.08, further supporting the conclusion that the model demonstrates an adequate fit to the data.

Regarding incremental fit indices, several indicators were reported which, when considered alongside the absolute fit measures, confirm that the model demonstrates a satisfactory fit. Specifically, the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) was 0.948, the Normed Fit Index (NFI) was 0.939, the Relative Fit Index (RFI) was 0.931, and the Incremental Fit Index (IFI) reached 0.954. All values exceed the recommended threshold of 0.90, indicating excellent model fit.

Finally, with respect to model parsimony, and given that the χ^2/df ratio although reasonable is not ideal, adjusted parsimony-based fit indices were also considered. The Parsimonious

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Normed Fit Index (PNFI) was 0.829, and the Parsimonious Goodness-of-Fit Index (PGFI) reached 0.761. Both values exceed the recommended reference levels of 0.50 and 0.60, respectively, further supporting the adequacy of the model.

With the model shown to align well with the theoretical framework, attention turns to the evaluation of the hypothesized relationships. For students enrolled in Early Childhood and Primary Education programs, neither gender nor academic year emerged as significant moderators in the relationships among the model's constructs. This finding, while notable, requires careful theoretical discussion.

In terms of the core dimensions measured by the instrument, a clear result emerges: effort expectancy, performance expectancy, and habitual use of AI all show a significant positive impact on the intention to use AI (see Table 3).

Table 3
Influence between dimensions.

Hypothesis	Relationship	β	B	SE	p	Status
H1	PE → BEH	0.42	0.47	0.18	.01	Confirmed
H2	EE → BEH	-	-	0.15	.04	Confirmed
H3	SI → BEH	-	-	0.05	.14	Rejected
H4	FC → BEH	-	-	0.23	0.14	Rejected
H4a	FC.Sexo → BI	0.19	0.27	0.42	.51	Rejected
H4b	FC.CURSO → BEH	-	-	0.13	.96	Rejected
H5	HM → BEH	0.09	0.08	0.08	.31	Rejected
H5a	HM.Sexo → BEH	-	-	0.38	.48	Rejected
H5b	HM.CURSO → BEH	0.03	0.01	0.12	.91	Rejected
H6	PV → BEH	-	-	0.04	.70	Rejected
H6a	PV.Sexo → BEH	-	-	0.23	.92	Rejected
H6b	PV.CURSO → BEH	0.03	0.01	0.08	.85	Rejected
H7	HT → BEH	0.67	0.43	0.06	.00	Confirmed
H7a	HT.Sexo → BEH	0.15	0.13	0.25	.59	Rejected
H7b	HT.CURSO → BEH	0.07	0.02	0.08	.77	Rejected

In this way, the relationships defined by the UTAUT2 model and previously described at the theoretical level are confirmed, with gender and academic year incorporated as moderating variables (see Figure 3).

Figura 3
Results

VII DISCUSIÓN

The findings elucidated within this investigation bear considerable import for the ongoing scholarly discourse within the field of educational technology. Their significance is twofold: they simultaneously interrogate and problematize established tenets within the extant literature while concurrently reinforcing and validating other foundational pillars of contemporary understanding. This dialectical contribution both challenging and affirming serves to refine the academic conversation surrounding technology adoption. Moreover, this research proffers a critically nuanced examination of the institutional role that universities are poised to play, and perhaps are currently neglecting, in the strategic promotion and pedagogically sound integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications within higher education and professional teacher preparation.

To contextualize these contributions, it is imperative to acknowledge the existing corpus of research. Preliminary investigations by scholars such as Bökrci and Çelik (2024), Lee (2023), and Skantz-Åberg et al. (2022) have robustly demonstrated that AI-powered tools can function as exceptionally efficacious instruments for the enhancement of academic performance and pedagogical efficacy. This positive impact has been observed from a dual perspective, encompassing both the student experience through personalized learning pathways and immediate feedback mechanisms and the faculty experience via the automation of administrative tasks and data-driven insights into student progress. A consequential corollary of this demonstrated utility, as noted in these studies, is a marked positive influence on the behavioral intentions of users, fostering a greater propensity to adopt and integrate AI solutions into their future academic or professional practices. The empirical data gathered in the present study demonstrates a clear consonance with these prior, foundational contributions. By replicating these core findings within a distinct geographical and institutional context (Andalusian universities), this work provides additional, corroborating empirical evidence, thereby lending further credence and

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robustness to conclusions that are gradually becoming established within the literature.

However, the academic conversation is far from monolithic. While a relatively broad and stable consensus has coalesced around the predictive power of performance expectancy the belief that the tool will enhance outcomes this study deliberately engages with a more contentious and less settled dimension: the expectancy of effort. This construct, which pertains to the perceived ease or difficulty associated with utilizing AI systems, is an arena characterized by greater scholarly divergence and theoretical debate. It is within this specific domain of inquiry that the results of our investigation yield their most valuable and distinctive insights. The data offers much-needed clarity and provides a firm empirical foundation that could potentially steer future interpretations and theoretical models toward a more coherent and unified direction, moving beyond the current state of conflicting findings.

A review of the literature reveals the diametrically opposed positions that characterize this debate. On one hand, a prominent camp of thought, represented by researchers such as Khechine et al. (2020) and Romero-Rodríguez et al. (2022), posits a straightforward positive correlation. Their work sustains the argument that a greater perceived ease of use of AI tools directly and positively impacts the user's intention to adopt them sustainably in the future. The underlying rationale, drawn from classic technology acceptance models, is that increased accessibility and user-friendliness of AI-based technologies significantly diminish the cognitive and practical effort required by prospective educators, thereby lowering the barrier to entry and increasing their willingness to embrace and continue utilizing these innovations.

Conversely, an emerging and more critical scholarly perspective, eloquently articulated by Alonso-Rodríguez (2024), introduces a crucial caveat. This viewpoint warns of a potential paradox wherein excessive simplicity and accessibility of AI interfaces might, within certain educational contexts, inadvertently cultivate counterproductive tendencies. These include over-reliance, superficial engagement with learning materials, and a heightened propensity for procrastination, as tasks can be completed with minimal intellectual investment. The findings of the present study offer compelling empirical support that aligns more closely with this latter, critical interpretation. Our data suggests that an excessively streamlined and simplified access to powerful AI tools might not unequivocally lead to acceptance but could, paradoxically, engender skepticism and doubts among future educators. These individuals, trained to value pedagogical depth and critical thinking, may perceive such ease as indicative of a lack of academic rigor or as a potential catalyst for ethical dilemmas concerning academic integrity. This critical finding carries profound practical implications. It underscores the absolute necessity of moving beyond mere provision of technology and toward the implementation of comprehensive, mandatory training programs. These programs must focus not only on operational competence but also on the ethical,

pedagogical, and critical dimensions of AI use, ensuring its appropriate application within educational environments. Furthermore, it highlights a critical avenue for future research: to examine whether such targeted instructional interventions can effectively mitigate skepticism and positively recalibrate perceptions and long-term usage patterns among educators-in-training.

Regarding the institutional dimension, the role of facilitating conditions the perceived institutional support and availability of resources merits specific discussion. It is documented that Andalusian universities have publicly and explicitly declared their commitment to championing the use of AI across both teaching and research functions. One might logically expect that such a pronounced institutional endorsement would manifest as a strong, significant predictor of adoption intention in our model. However, its impact was not statistically evident. This discrepancy invites interpretation. The literature provides a potential explanation by emphasizing that the mere provision of technology is insufficient. Zhang et al. (2023) aptly stress that overly simplistic access, when decoupled from adequate guidance, robust ethical frameworks, and clear pedagogical integration, can actually provoke social criticism and foster public distrust. The misuse, or perceived trivialization, of a powerful tool like AI can drastically diminish its perceived value and legitimacy, causing it to be relegated to the realm of entertainment rather than being taken seriously as an educational instrument. Kalniņa et al. (2024) provide a pertinent contemporary example in the widespread popularity of using AI for generating images in specific artistic styles (e.g., "Ghibli"), a phenomenon that, while demonstrating accessibility, remains largely divorced from core educational objectives and may even reinforce perceptions of AI as a toy rather than a tool.

Consequently, and based on this combined theoretical premise and our empirical results, the most salient finding regarding facilitating conditions is the absence of a significant influence on the future intention to use AI among the cohort of student teachers studied. This null result opens up rich and complex avenues for scholarly discussion, particularly when examined through the lens of the sample's specific characteristics. The participant pool was drawn from a diverse set of Andalusian universities, institutions that likely exhibit disparities in funding, technological infrastructure, and specific support mechanisms. Yet, surprisingly, these potential institutional variations did not translate into statistically significant differences in intention. This suggests that individual perceptions and pedagogical beliefs may outweigh institutional factors in this specific context. It would therefore be a valuable endeavor for subsequent research to conduct a more granular analysis, perhaps employing multi-group analysis or case studies, to explore whether these latent institutional differences emerge more clearly when universities are examined individually and qualitatively.

Furthermore, this study meticulously examined the potential moderating effects of two key demographic variables: gender and academic year. The findings here also challenge some

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previous assumptions. Although Zhang et al. (2023) had previously identified gender as a potential differentiating factor in technology adoption models, our data did not reveal significant differences in intention or perception across gender lines. A plausible explanation for this discrepancy may reside in the unique nature of the sample. The participants, all enrolled in teacher training programs (Early Childhood and Primary Education), likely share a strong common set of academic interests, professional values, and future-oriented goals. This powerful shared identity and common purpose may effectively neutralize or supersede the sociodemographic variations in perceptions or intentions that might be observed in a more heterogeneous population sample. This finding contributes to an ongoing debate in the literature regarding the primacy of professional socialization versus innate demographic characteristics in shaping technology acceptance.

This null result related to academic year, however, invites a more critical and concerning reflection on the structure and content of the teacher training curricula themselves. Both the Early Childhood Education and Primary Education degrees in the sampled universities include at least one mandatory subject dedicated to technological resources in educational contexts. A reasonable and logical expectation would be that progressive exposure to this curriculum would engender noticeably different attitudes, higher self-efficacy, and more sophisticated behaviors regarding advanced technologies like AI as students advance from their first to their final year. However, no such developmental differentiation was detected. This absence of effect is telling and points toward two disconcerting possibilities. First, it may indicate that the current structure and content of the technology-related subjects are failing to effectively equip student teachers with the necessary knowledge, critical skills, and practical confidence to interact meaningfully with AI in educational settings. The instruction may be focused on more traditional digital tools, leaving a gap in addressing cutting-edge AI applications. Second, and more systemically, it raises serious concerns about institutional and curricular responsibility. It suggests that despite the existence of a relevant course, the overarching curricula and syllabi have not been proactively updated to explicitly and thoughtfully address AI-specific content, its ethical implications, and its pedagogical integration. This critical lack of curricular alignment and modernization likely acts as a contributing factor to the persistent skepticism towards AI found in this cohort and fails to empower future teachers with a toolkit that, as overwhelming evidence suggests, can significantly enhance differentiated instruction, administrative efficiency, and inclusive educational practices.

Shifting the focus to motivational aspects, the study also yielded counterintuitive results concerning hedonic motivation the fun or pleasure derived from using a technology. The prevailing literature, as seen in the work of Rahimi & Mosalli (2024) and Alonso-Rodríguez (2024), predominantly suggests a positive relationship where intrinsic enjoyment fosters a stronger intention to use. Our study did not confirm this expected relationship. A compelling explanation can be woven

from the earlier discussed findings regarding effort expectancy. The perceived resistance and skepticism stemming from AI's excessive ease of use appear to create a paradox that suppresses the anticipated positive effect of enjoyment. In other words, the potential for fun is seemingly overridden by ethical and pedagogical concerns, leading to a scenario where simplicity does not breed engagement but rather caution. This nuanced interplay between perceived ease, skepticism, and motivation represents a significant contribution to the theoretical model and warrants further investigation.

The absence of a significant hedonic motivation effect warrants deeper contextualization within the specific cultural and institutional landscape of Andalusian teacher education. Unlike contexts where intrinsic enjoyment has been shown to drive technology adoption (Rahimi & Mosalli, 2024), the Andalusian pre-service teachers in this sample appear to navigate a complex tension between perceived utility and ethical responsibility. This cultural-pedagogical orientation, characteristic of Spanish teacher training programs that emphasize critical pedagogy and social responsibility (Ruiz Viruel et al., 2025), may suppress the hedonic dimension in favor of more pragmatic or duty-bound considerations. Furthermore, the null effect of gender as a moderator in this study stands in stark contrast to findings from other cultural contexts. For instance, Zhang et al. (2023) documented significant gender-based differences in technology anxiety and adoption patterns in Asian educational settings, while Monzon & Hair (2025) found minimal gender effects in North American samples. These divergent results suggest that gender's role in AI acceptance may be culturally contingent rather than universal. In the Andalusian context specifically, the feminization of the teaching profession (with over 70% of education degree enrollments being female) may create a professional culture where gender differences are attenuated by shared pedagogical values and career expectations. These findings carry direct implications for curricular reform. Rather than assuming that making AI tools "fun" or "engaging" will drive adoption, Andalusian universities must prioritize ethical frameworks, critical AI literacy, and pedagogically grounded training that aligns with the professional identity and values of future teachers. Generic technology integration courses appear insufficient; instead, discipline-specific modules that address AI's role in inclusive education, differentiated instruction, and ethical classroom practice are urgently needed to bridge the gap between institutional AI promotion and actual classroom implementation.

In stark contrast to these null and paradoxical findings, one variable emerged with unequivocal and robust predictive power: habitual use. The self-reported frequency of current AI use was the strongest positive predictor of future intention to use it in educational contexts. This result is entirely coherent with the theoretical framework of the study and reinforces a well-established pattern in behavioral intention research. From a domain-specific perspective, the findings of Cukurova et al. (2023) help explain this strong relationship. They note that student teachers are acutely aware of AI's potential to reduce

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their administrative and planning workload, particularly by automating repetitive, mechanical tasks such as quiz generation, material adaptation, and preliminary feedback. Furthermore, those students who engage with AI more frequently are likely to develop a more sophisticated and nuanced understanding of its capabilities that extends beyond mere convenience. This includes an appreciation for its role in supporting inclusive education practices for instance, by effortlessly facilitating the adaptation of learning materials for students with diverse special educational needs (Suconota-Pintado et al., 2023). This deeper, experience-based understanding of AI's transformative potential, therefore, translates directly into a stronger intention to integrate it into their future professional practice.

In conclusion, the most critical and defining aspects of this study's findings revolve around the non-significant moderating effects. The proposition that gender and academic year would meaningfully alter the strength of the relationships within the adoption model was a central hypothesis, and its rejection forces a significant reconsideration of certain assumptions. This outcome opens several critical lines of inquiry for both the present study and the wider literature review. Regarding gender, the scientific community lacks a clear consensus on its role as a definitive moderator in technology adoption. While Zhang et al. (2023) present compelling evidence for differentiated usage patterns and interests linked to gender, our research aligns more closely with a growing body of work by scholars such as Monzon & Hair (2025), Li et al. (2025), and Chiu et al. (2023), which argues that in the specific context of professional and academic technology use, gender distinctions are becoming less pronounced or are being neutralized by other, more powerful factors.

To justify the absence of moderation, one must also consider the overarching ethical debate clouding AI in education. As Kazley et al. (2025) argue, the ethics of AI use are highly questionable in pedagogical settings, where its application can often be conflated with academic dishonesty or "cheating" by both faculty and students, regardless of gender. This pervasive ethical ambiguity creates a universal field of caution that likely affects all users equally, thereby suppressing potential gender-based variation. Therefore, while this study disproves gender's influence on the valuation and acceptance of AI, it crucially does not preclude the possibility of gendered differences in the specific modalities of use or application preferences, a possibility left open by scholars like De-Vicente-Yagüe-Jara et al. (2023) and representing a fertile ground for future qualitative research.

Finally, the most damning institutional critique arising from this study pertains to the null effect of the academic year. The fact that students in their final year are no more prepared or inclined to use AI meaningfully than those in their first year is a stark indictment of the current state of initial teacher training curricula. Updating official degree syllabi is a notoriously slow process, fraught with bureaucratic inertia and often lagging years behind technological advancements. While modules on general "technological resources" exist, the findings suggest

that explicit, critical content on Artificial Intelligence remains absent or woefully inadequate. This failure has serious consequences. It directly disadvantages universities, particularly those like the Andalusian institutions in this study that are actively managing public investment aimed at integrating AI across the university spectrum. While this investment is not entirely lost as it may benefit STEM fields more directly it is effectively wasted within the specific context of teacher education. The students graduate without the competencies needed to harness a transformative technology, thus perpetuating a cycle of skepticism and underutilization and ultimately failing in the institution's mission to prepare future-ready educators. This study therefore serves as a urgent call to action for a comprehensive and accelerated revision of teacher training curricula to ensure the meaningful, critical, and ethical integration of AI, thereby empowering the next generation of educators.

VIII CONCLUSIONS

This study explored the factors influencing the intention to use Artificial Intelligence (AI) among pre-service teachers, drawing upon the UTAUT2 model and incorporating sociodemographic moderators such as gender and academic year. The findings contribute to the growing body of research on AI in education, offering both confirmation of established theories and new insights into contextual variations within teacher education.

Key constructs such as performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and habit were found to significantly and positively influence the intention to continue using AI in educational settings. Among these, habitual use emerged as the most decisive predictor, indicating that familiarity and routine engagement with AI tools are critical drivers of long-term adoption. This underscores the importance of promoting early and sustained exposure to AI in teacher education programs.

In contrast, constructs such as facilitating conditions and hedonic motivation did not demonstrate a significant influence on intention to use AI in this sample. These findings challenge prior research and suggest that ease of access and enjoyment may not be sufficient motivators when not accompanied by deeper understanding or pedagogical alignment. The absence of significant moderation by gender or academic year further suggests that institutional and programmatic factors such as curriculum content may play a more important role than individual demographic characteristics.

Of particular concern is the lack of curricular impact from educational technology courses, which, despite their inclusion in degree programs, appear to have limited influence on students' perceptions and intentions regarding AI. This highlights the urgent need for teacher education institutions to update course content to reflect emerging technologies and prepare future educators for their responsible and effective use.

Ultimately, this study provides a critical perspective on how pre-service teachers interact with AI, emphasizing the importance of both habitual engagement and targeted pedagogical training. For institutions seeking to integrate AI

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meaningfully into education, these findings advocate for curriculum reform, increased institutional support, and more intentional efforts to bridge the gap between technological innovation and teaching practice.

8.1. Future Research

Based on the findings and limitations of this study, several lines of future research are proposed:

Design and Validation of Formative Processes in Educational AI: Future studies should focus on the development and empirical validation of structured training programs in Educational Artificial Intelligence. These should integrate both technical skills and pedagogical strategies, enabling pre-service teachers to engage critically and effectively with AI tools in classroom contexts.

Longitudinal Studies on AI Use: Research should assess whether early exposure to AI during teacher training translates into sustained, pedagogically meaningful use in professional practice.

Institutional Comparative Analysis: Further research could investigate how differences between universities (e.g., resources, instructional design, curriculum integration) influence the effectiveness of AI-related training and the intention to use AI.

Impact of AI-Specific Curriculum Reform: Studies should examine whether updating educational technology syllabi to explicitly address AI concepts and applications results in measurable changes in students' attitudes, competencies, and behaviors.

Mixed-Methods Approaches: Complementing quantitative models with qualitative inquiry (e.g., interviews, classroom observations) could provide deeper insights into how pre-service teachers perceive and apply AI in real educational scenarios.

These lines of research will be essential for advancing the field of AI in education and for aligning teacher preparation programs with the digital transformation of educational systems.

8.2. Limitations

Despite the contributions of this study, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the use of a non-probabilistic convenience sample limits the generalizability of the findings, as the sample may not fully represent the diversity of pre-service teacher populations across different regions or institutions. Second, the cross-sectional design captures data at a single moment in time, preventing any assessment of how attitudes and intentions toward AI might evolve with increased exposure or professional experience. Additionally, the reliance on self-reported measures introduces the risk of bias, including social desirability effects and potential inaccuracies in participants' self-assessments. The absence of qualitative data also limits the depth of interpretation, as it precludes a more nuanced understanding of the contextual and experiential factors influencing AI use. Furthermore, although gender and academic year were examined as moderating variables, other

potentially relevant influences such as prior technological training, pedagogical orientation, or institutional support were not included. Finally, while the study involved participants from several Andalusian universities, it did not control for differences in curriculum design, access to resources, or instructional strategies related to AI, which could have significantly shaped students' perceptions and intentions.

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